

Effects of Inorganic Fertilizers on Soybean (*Glycine max (L) Merr*) Varieties in Ogbomosho, South West, Nigeria

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Abstract

Crops response to nutrients effect in terms of growth and yield; soybean is not an exception to the major nutrients. Hence, a pot experiment was conducted in Ogbomosho, Oyo State, Nigeria to determine the response of ten soybean varieties to NPK fertilizers. The treatments are: NPK application; (NAF-No fertilizer application), (P+K-Phosphorus and potassium), (P+N-Phosphorus and Nitrogen), (P; phosphorus alone) and (N+P+K application). It was a factorial experiment, laid in Completely Randomized Design with four replicates. Data collected are: plant height and number of leaves, flowers and pods, weights of; fresh and dry biomass, root and dry matter; and nutrient uptake. Data were subjected to Analysis of Variance and treatment means were separated using (DMRT^α_{0.05}). In conclusion, the interactions between the two factors were highly significant on the growth parameters and nutrient uptakes. The interactive effects on soybean variety TGm1057 under NFA produced the highest fresh shoot and root weights, while under (P+K) application, TGm1052 had the highest fresh root weight. Variety TGm1057 under NFA has the highest N uptake while variety TGm1052 under (P+K) application had the highest P uptake. But TGm1057 under (P+N) application had the highest N and K uptake. The highest soybean pod yield was obtained from variety TGm1052 under phosphorus and potassium (P+K) application while TGm1057 had the least yield under the same fertilizer application. In conclusion, it can be recommended that soybean variety TGm1057 be cultivated with little or no N fertilizer but with phosphorus and potassium fertilizer application for optimal pod yield.

Keywords: Different, Fertilizers, Response, Soybean, Varieties

Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) is an important leguminous and oilseed crop that is widely grown because it is adaptable to

different agro-ecological zones (Agarwal and Singh, 2015). Soybean is the world's leading source of protein and oil. It has the highest protein content of all food crops and is second

only to groundnut in terms of oil content among grain leguminous crop (Ikeogu and Nwofia, 2013). Soybean is a plant that possesses the traits such as; high nutritional value, resistance to diseases and pests, and lower susceptibility to lodging compared to other legumes (Gawęda *et al.* 2016). It is one of the most important fodder plants which account for about 58% of total oilseed production worldwide and 69% of protein in the diet of livestock animals (Borawska *et al.* 2014). Soybean is high of polyunsaturated fatty acids, refers to as one of the most valuable oilseed plants (Agarwal, 2013; Medic *et al.* 2014). Due to its high nutritional value and beneficial effect on the soil, there is increasing interest in soybean cultivation (Jaskulska *et al.* 2017).

Soybean is among the major industrial and food crops grown almost in all agro-ecological zones in Nigeria. The crop is successfully grown in Nigeria with low agricultural input; this has made its cultivation to be expanded coupled with its nutritional and economic importance among other diverse local uses. The seeds contain about 20% oil on a dry matter basis and this is 85% unsaturated and cholesterol-free. The rapid growth of both the poultry and food processing industries in the past decade has also increased demand for soybean in Nigeria (Xiang, Yong, Yang, Wan, Gong, Cui & Lei , 2012).

However, its cultivation and production increased as farmers were aware of the potential of this crop for cash, food and for soil fertility improvement and Striga control (Omoigui *et al.*, 2020). There are several soybean varieties; Notable promising soybean varieties for both southern and, northern guinea, savanna and sudan savanna zones are: TGX 1448-2E, TGX1951-3F, TGX 1904-6F, TGX 1987-62F and TGX 1987-10F. However, it is important to choose a

variety suitable to particular agro ecological zone. Hence, variety selection should be done based on the time to maturity, yield potential, susceptibility to stem lodging, drought tolerance, and resistance to pests and diseases. The maturity period should be considered when choosing a variety, suited to your geographical zone. Although late maturing varieties have the potential to increase in yield, but the danger of late-season drought is eminent (Omoigui *et al.*, 2020).

Despite the high yielding potentials of soybean across the production zones, there are number of reasons identified for declining productivity of the soybean viz., heavy or very low rainfall, pests and diseases attack, pests to diseases susceptibility, imbalanced use of fertilizers, soil fertility problems, low soil organic matter, water stress, poor management (Walikar *et al.*, 2018); Lu and Tian, 2017).

Moreover, the problem of soybean response to the major nutrients; nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (NPK) is soil has received little or not much research focus in most soybean producing zones in Nigeria. According to Mourtzinis *et al.*, (2018), soybean seed production requires larger amounts of N compared to cereal crops because of its chemical composition, however, soybean response to N fertilization has not always increased seed yield. Moreover, N fertilizer application reduces the biological N fixation (BNF) activity by inhibiting the process (Mourtzinis *et al.*, (2018). Soybean plants assimilate a large amount of nitrogen (about 330 kg N ha⁻¹ for a yield of 4 t ha⁻¹) during vegetation period, and the amount of N adopted in a plant is highly correlated with the soybean seed yield (), as well as with the chemical composition of soybean grains (Gai *et al.*, 2016; Popović *et al.*, 2016).

On the other hand, Phosphorus is a

vital element in crop production which performs important role for many characteristics of plant growth such as sugar and starch utilization, photosynthesis use, cell division and organization, nodule formation, root development, flower initiation and seed and fruit development (Gangasuresh *et al.*, 2010; Sanginga *et al.*, 2015). The role of Potassium (K) is essential as factor for optimal production of soybean crops (Redel, Escudey Alvear & Borie, 2011). It is the most abundant cation in plants involved in many physiological processes which include activating over 80 enzymes, regulating cellular osmotic water potential, photosynthesis, protein metabolism, and helping plants adapt to environmental stresses (Walikar, Bhan, Giri, Dubey & Agrawal, 2018).

From the various established works about soybean response to NPK, there is need to be soybean varietal specific in their response interm of yields and other growth parameters. Hence, the aims of the work are: to assess the response of different soybean varieties to various inorganic fertilizers in Ogbomoso agro-ecology and to identify the soybean variety and the inorganic fertilizer that would have highest significant effect on soybean performance.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site: A screen-house experiment was carried out at Faculty of Agriculture, Ladoké Akintola (LAUTECH) Teaching and Research Farm, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, located on longitude 4° 30' E and latitude 10° 5' N. The climate hot, humid, tropical, of southern guinea savannah of Nigeria with mean temperature of 27°C, annual rainfall of 1400mm and marked with wet and dry season.

Soil sampling and pre-planting soil analysis:

Soil samples were collected at a depth 0 – 20 cm from the Teaching and Research Farm of University of Technology (LAUTECH). The soil collected was used to filled the pots (5 kg polythene bag size). Parts of the composite soil samples were air dried and processed for physical and chemical analyses.

Source of Soybean seeds and fertilizer: Ten varieties of soybean seeds were obtained from the genetic resources center, IITA, Ibadan. The varieties are; (TGm 1002 = V₁, TGm 1052 = V₂, TGm 1057 = V₃, TGm 1434 = V₄, TGm 1537 = V₅, TGm 1816 = V₆, TGm 1817 = V₇, TGm 264 = V₈, TGm 4360 = V₉, TGm 623 = V₁₀).

The following were nutrients evaluated: Phosphorus (P), Nitrogen (N) and Potassium (K). Nitrogen was supplied using urea, while phosphorus and potassium were supplied using SSP and MOP respectively. Basal application of fertilizers were done at; 20kg nitrogen, 40kg P₂O₅ and 20kg K₂O, per hectare respectively, before planting.

Fertilizer application/treatments application: The fertilizers recommended rates for the experiment, are: Urea-0.11 g/ 5 kg pots, MOP-0.06 g/ 5kg pot and SSP-0.24 g/ 5 kg pots; the treatments are: NAF= No fertilizer application, P+K = Phosphorus and potassium application, P+N = Phosphorus and nitrogen application and P only = Phosphorus application alone and NPK application.

Experimental treatments, design and layout: The pots/ bags for the experiment were arranged in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with each treatment replicated four times, given a total number of two hundred (200) experimental units or pots.

Sowing and other agronomic practices: Four seeds were sown per pot at a depth of 2 cm and latter thinned to two per pot, manual irrigation were carried out except on raining days and weeding was regularly carried out.

Cypermethrin was applied was applied to control pests.

Data Collection and analysis: The following data were collected biweekly after sowing: plant height (cm), numbers of leaf, number of pods, plant weight and root weight (g), Nutrient uptake (nitrogen, potassium and phosphorus (NPK) uptake.

All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means were compared with Least Significance Difference at 5% probability level.

Results and Discussion

Experimental soil used: The chemical and constituents and the particle sizes results of

the experimental soil used reveal that the soil pH is slightly acidic (6.50) while the soil organic carbon and nitrogen are (0.55 and 0.05 g kg⁻¹) very low but the available phosphorus was (105.94 mg kg⁻¹) very high. The potassium and calcium of this soil are of low values; (0.17 and 3.39 cmol kg⁻¹) while Mg and Na are 0.40 and 0.08 cmol kg⁻¹, respectively. The micronutrients (iron, manganese, copper and zinc) values ranged from 6.79 – 273.87 cmol kg⁻¹ of which Fe was very high. The exchangeable cations (K, Ca, Mg, Na) values ranged from 0.08 – 3.39 cmol kg⁻¹ while the exchangeable acidity was infinitesimal. The values of sand, silt and clay particles showed that the soil textural class was loamy sand (Table 1).

Table 1: The chemical composition and the particle sizes of the experimental soil used

Soil pH, Org. Carbon, TN and Available Phosphorus	Exchangeable cations (cmol kg ⁻¹)	Micronutrients (mg kg ⁻¹)
pH (H ₂ O)	6.50	K 0.17 Fe 273.87
Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	0.55	Ca 3.39 Mn 150.20
Total Nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	0.05	Mg 0.40 Cu 6.79
Av. Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	105.94	Na 0.08 Zn 198.80
	Exchangeable acidity	0.00 cmol kg ⁻¹
	Sand Silt Clay	Textural class
Particle size distribution (g kg⁻¹)	82	5.0 12.0 Loamy sand soil

Soybean number of leaf: At 6 weeks after sowing (6WAS), there was varietal significant difference in the number of leaf per the fertilizers application, the mean numbers of leaf of the soybean plant ranged from 5 – 7 while under the various fertilizers application, the number of leaf ranged from 5 – 6. It was observed that soybean varieties under P application had 6 leaves (mean value of 5.93) the application of P and N had the lowest number of 5 leaves (mean value; 5.10), while variety 8 (V8 = TGM 264) had 7 leaves (mean value; 6.80) and the least number of leaf (4.70) was observed with variety 7 (V₇= TGM 1817). However, there was no significant

interaction effect between the fertilizer application and soybean variety on the number of leaves at 6 weeks after sowing (Figure 1).

Plant height: At 6WAS, on average, all the soybean varieties the least (17.27 cm) and the highest (19.12 cm) plant heights under P+N and NFA fertilizer application, respectively, however, while on the variety basis of responding to fertilizer application the TGM 1817 had the least plant height (15.05cm) and the highest (25.35 cm) plant height was observed with variety TGM 264. There was significant varietal effect as well as significant interaction between the fertilizers and the variety (Figure 1).

Bars represent the $LSD_{0.005}$

Figure 1: Response of plant height and number of leaf different soybean variety to different fertilizer types at 6WAS

Bars represent the standard error (SE)

(NAF) = No fertilizer application, (P+K) = Phosphorus and potassium application,

(P+N) = Phosphorus and nitrogen application and (P) = Phosphorus application alone (NPK) application

Figure 2: Number of pod of ten varieties of soybean as influenced by fertilizer types

Bars represent the standard error (SE)

(NAF) = No fertilizer application, (P+K) = Phosphorus and potassium application,

(P+N) = Phosphorus and nitrogen application and (P) = Phosphorus application alone (NPK) application

Soybean variety	Soybean yield parameters weights (g/pot)					
	Fresh yield parameter weights			Dry yield parameter weights		
	Root	Total biomass	Root	Pod	Total biomass	Dry matter
TGm 1002	0.73	5.25	0.23	8.77	3.62	1.926
TGm 1052	1.76	6.99	0.28	10.13	4.68	2.528
TGm 1057	1.65	8.54	0.35	10.39	5.59	2.970
TGm 1434	1.02	6.007	0.22	7.81	3.36	1.792
TGm 1537	0.98	5.27	0.26	8.39	3.60	1.929
TGm 1816	1.48	7.31	0.36	9.39	4.59	2.475
TGm 1817	1.40	7.50	0.30	9.52	4.72	2.507
TGm 264	1.65	8.78	0.42	11.46	6.81	3.615
TGm 4360	1.57	7.60	0.32	8.90	4.30	2.309
TGm 623	1.47	6.83	0.21	8.68	3.68	1.948
Variety LSD _{0.05}	0.18**	0.77**	0.07**	0.44**	0.31**	0.50 **
Fertilizer*variety LSD _{0.05}	0.41**	1.72**	0.15**	0.98**	0.56	1.12 **

Under the application of NFA soybean varieties TG_m1057 and 623 highest number of pods while TG_m1434 and 4360 has the least number of pods under the NFA application (Figure 2).

Yield parameters: Under the applications of all these fertilizer types, the fresh and dry root weights of the ten soybean varieties ranged from 0.73 – 1.76g (fresh) and 0.22 – 0.42g (dry), respectively. Similarly, variety TGm1002 had the lowest total fresh biomass (5.25g) while TGm264 had the highest total biomass. Meanwhile, this pattern was not followed other yield parameters that were observed under all the fertilizer types. However, the pod yield ranged from TGm 1002 (8.77g) - TGm264 (11.46g) as average pod yield under the different fertilizer application, Howbeit, there were significant effect of these fertilizers on the yield parameters both on each soybean variety so also the interaction of the fertilizer types on the variety (Table 2).

Table 2: The response of different varieties of soybean to different fertilizer types

*, ** significant at 5%, 1% and 0.1%

probability levels respectively, ns= not significant

(NAF)= No fertilizer application, (P+K) = Phosphorus and potassium application, (P+N) = Phosphorus and nitrogen application and (P) = Phosphorus application alone (NPK) application.

Interaction effects of variety and fertilizer:

The interaction effects of variety and fertilizer on mean performance of soybean; for root, pods and shoot of soybean (Table 3), showed that there were significant interactive effects between the variety and fertilizer application, and these effects are noticeable on the fresh shoot and root weights of variety 3 (**TGm 1057**) and under NAF (No fertilizer application) treatment, which makes it the best plant and treatment that aids root development. Also the interaction between the variety and treatment had significant effects on the dry shoot and dry root weights of variety 3 (**TGm 1057**) under P+N application (Table 3).

Table 3: Interaction effects of different variety and fertilizer types on growth and yield performance

Interaction Variety + fertilizer types	Number of flowers	Interaction	Fresh shoot weight (g)	Interaction	Fresh root weight (g)	Interaction	Root length (cm)	Interaction	Dry shoot weight (g)
V ₂ (NFA)	7.75 ^a	V ₃ (NFA)	10.87 ^a	V ₂ (P+K)	2.96 ^a	V ₂ (P+K)	15.50 ^a	V ₈ (P+N)	3.76 ^a
V ₂ (NPK)	7.25 ^a	V ₉ (P+K)	10.62 ^a	V ₁₀ (NFA)	2.88 ^a	V ₂ (NPK)	15.25 ^a	V ₈ (NFA)	3.64 ^a
V ₁ (P+K)	7.00 ^a	V ₇ (NPK)	10.48 ^a	V ₃ (NFA)	2.85 ^a	V ₄ (NPK)	13.00 ^a	V ₃ (P+N)	3.56 ^a
V ₁₀ (P+N)	0.50 ^{bc}	V ₁₀ (NFA)	3.49 ^{bc}	V ₅ (NPK)	0.74 ^{bc}	V ₁ (P)	3.75 ^{bc}	V ₄ (P+K)	1.12 ^{bc}
V ₁₀ (P)	0.50 ^{bc}	V ₂ (P+N)	3.45 ^{bc}	V ₄ (P+N)	0.69 ^{bc}	V ₄ (P+N)	3.60 ^{bc}	V ₂ (P+N)	1.11 ^{bc}
V ₁₀ (NPK)	0.50 ^{bc}	V ₉ (NFA)	3.00 ^{bc}	V ₁ (P)	0.23 ^{bc}	V ₆ (NPK)	3.00 ^{bc}	V ₁₀ (P+K)	1.10 ^{bc}
SE (Df =59)	±0.79		±0.63		±0.15		±1.08		±0.35

Means with the same letter are not significantly different. SE = Standard Error, Df = Degree of Freedom

(NAF) = No fertilizer application, (P+K) = Phosphorus and potassium application, (P+N) = Phosphorus and nitrogen application and (P) = Phosphorus application alone (NPK) application, TGm

1002 = V₁, TGm 1052 = V₂, TGm 1057 = V₃, TGm 1434 = V₄, TGm 1537 = V₅, TGm 1816 = V₆, TGm 1817 = V₇, TGm 264 = V₈, TGm 4360 = V₉, TGm 623 = V₁₀

Table 4: Interaction effect of variety and fertilizer on the nutrient uptakes of soybean

Interaction + Variety fertilizer types	N uptake (%)	Interaction	P uptake (%)	Interaction	K uptake (%)	Interaction	NPK uptake (%)
V ₃ (P+N)	0.10 ^a	V ₂ (NAF)	0.01 ^a	V ₃ (P+N)	0.06 ^a	V ₃ (P+N)	0.04 ^a
V ₃ (NAF)	0.08 ^a	V ₂ (P+K)	0.01 ^a	V ₆ (P+K)	0.04 ^b	V ₃ (NPK)	0.03 ^b
V ₆ (NAF)	0.08 ^a	V ₆ (P+K)	0.01 ^{bc}	V ₇ (NPK)	0.04 ^b	V ₂ (P+N)	0.03 ^b
V ₁₀ (P)	0.03 ^{bc}	V ₆ (NPK)	0.003 ^{bc}	V ₅ (P+N)	0.01 ^{bc}	V ₄ (P+N)	0.01 ^{bc}
V ₁ (P+K)	0.03 ^{bc}	V ₄ (P+N)	0.003 ^{bc}	V ₆ (NPK)	0.01 ^{bc}	V ₆ (NPK)	0.003 ^{bc}
V ₆ (NPK)	0.02 ^{bc}	V ₁ (NPK)	0.003 ^{bc}	V ₅ (NAF)	0.003 ^{bc}	V ₅ (NAF)	0.001 ^{bc}
SE (Df= 59)	±0.01		±0.001		±0.004		±0.004

Means with the same letter are not significantly different, SE = Standard Error

(NAF) = No fertilizer application, (P+K) = Phosphorus and potassium application, (P+N) = Phosphorus and nitrogen application and (P) = Phosphorus application alone (NPK) application, TGm 1002 = V₁, TGm 1052 = V₂, TGm 1057 = V₃, TGm 1434 = V₄, TGm 1537 = V₅, TGm 1816 = V₆, TGm 1817 = V₇, TGm 264 = V₈, TGm 4360 = V₉, TGm 623 = V₁₀

Discussion

The availability of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) among other nutrients in soil are essential for the growth and yield of crops generally (Broch & Ranno, 2012). However, deficiency of phosphorus has been identified as the most limiting nutrient in soybean production as proved in this trial which corroborated Karikari *et al.*, (2015) findings. This may be attributed to the immobility of P in soils (Table 2). Nitrogen is less needed nutrient for soybean due to its ability to fix nitrogen, but most soils in the tropics are low in nitrogen (Table 2). However, nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizer application among other nutrients will have a residual effect on the successive crops grown on such soils (Xiang, Yong, Yang, Wan, Go, Lei, 2012).

Plant height was significantly affected by phosphorus and potassium fertilizer as noticed in the interaction with the soybean variety. TGM264 produced the tallest plant while TGM1816 produced the shortest plant under these two nutrients application. At the end of the experiment, maximum plant height of 25cm was recorded (Figure 1). The pot experiment thus confirmed the results of the field experiment where increase levels of potassium resulted in taller plants as reported by Snyder (2000). These findings are similar to those of Qureshi *et al* (2010) who found a significant increase in plant height due to phosphorus fertilizer application, as also reported by Qureshi, Beg and Siddiq, (2003). The highest soybean seed yield was obtained from variety TGM 1052 under phosphorus and potassium (P+K) application while TGM1057 had the lowest yield under the same fertilizer application. The result is in agreement with that of Pauline *et al.* (2010), and Aise *et al.* (2011) who reported a similar finding on soybean seed yield application of P+K fertilizer. According to IITA (2000)

report, and Popovic *et al.* (2016), other factors such as rainfall distribution, among other factors, substantially modify the quantity and quality of soybean seed yield. The soybean seed yield reduction at the lowest and highest P- fertilizer application was been recorded because, the growth and development of soybean was influenced by little or excess of phosphorus as reported by Xiang *et al.*, (2012). More conclusive results on yield responses of soybean were obtained in experiment conducted by Qureshi, Beg and Siddiq, (2003), where the yield was increased. Nutrients uptake pattern by these varieties of soybean revealed that phosphorus uptake was significantly affected by the use of different fertilizers source and soybean cultivars. The uptake of nutrients was significantly related to the total biomass produced by a cultivar, the increase in P uptake with the application of phosphorus over control (NFA) was significant. This showed that the application of P to soybean improved the efficiency of cultivars in accumulating more P, N and K (Mustafa, Darwesh & Luay, 2013).

From this trial, it can be deduced and recommended **that** this finding provides evidence that the application of P fertilizer positively influenced soybean growth and yield. And that soybean cultivar TGM1052 with highest performance under (P+K) fertilizers application is recommended for cultivation especially in soil with low nitrogen.

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